

ATTORNEY-CLIENT PRIVILEGE**Mamaeva Makbal****Independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Law****E-mail: mmakbal85@mail.ru****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236889>**

Abstract: In this article, the author comprehensively studied the main aspects of the development of the institution of attorney-client privilege in the conditions of modern Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. In particular, it is noted that this norm is provided for in international acts, including the UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners, etc. Also, the author, in organizational and functional terms, covers in sufficient detail the problems of ensuring the safety of attorney-client privilege as the basis of their legal status and independence. In the course of preparing the scientific work, some examples of foreign legislation, including the United States and the Russian Federation, were studied. Based on the results of the analysis of the institute of attorney-client privilege, theoretical conclusions and conclusions are presented.

Keywords: advocacy, attorney, defender, criminal process, attorney-client privilege, witness immunity, proof, evidence.

Introduction.

An important feature of advocacy is an attorney-client privilege. There is no need to talk about his inviolability, his importance, because this is an axiom in the modern understanding of advocacy. The regime of attorney-client privilege is determined by Article 9 “On the Bar” [1].

The legislation prohibits the interrogation of a lawyer as a witness in connection with the provision of legal assistance, and also establishes certain guarantees for the confidentiality of a lawyer-client, which are associated with a special procedure for conducting operational-search activities and investigative actions against a lawyer [2].

The Code of Criminal Procedure gives the accused the right to have private and confidential meetings with the defense counsel, including before the first interrogation of the accused, without limiting their number and duration (Part 2, Article 53 of the Code of Criminal Procedure).

This rule is in line with the guidelines set out in paragraph 93 of the Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners, according to which convicted persons who are not convicted for the purpose of protection should, whenever possible, be entitled to free legal advice. the opinion of the defender who undertook to defend himself, drawing up and handing him confidential instructions. However, the meetings of these persons should take place “out of earshot of the police or prison officials” [3].

A strict ban on uncontrolled interference in the sphere of trust between a lawyer and a client is a reliable guarantee of the independence of a lawyer, since in such a legal regime he can collect any information within the law and without fear for the confidentiality of the data received.

Issues of protecting lawyer secrecy.

One of the fundamental principles of the functioning of this institution has always been the principle of ensuring the confidentiality of the relationship between the principal and the lawyer. Lawyer secrecy means any information related to the provision of legal assistance by a

lawyer to his client. The institution of the bar is called upon to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, and in this regard, the main essence of lawyer secrecy is revealed, which consists in the impossibility of obliging a lawyer to testify against his client. Thus, the advocacy is characterized by a strictly defined procedural role that does not allow any authoritative interpretations.

Meanwhile, for example, in the Russian Federation, a search, inspection and seizure of a lawyer can only be carried out after a criminal case has been initiated against him, on the basis of a judge's decision and in the presence of a member of the council of the bar association who ensures the inviolability of lawyer secrecy. In addition, the judge's decision must necessarily indicate the specific data that served as the basis for its issuance and the specific searched objects. Seizure of other objects, as well as their photographing, filming, video recording and other fixation are not allowed [4].

In this regard, the question arises to what extent the lawyer's secret is protected by law in the event of its violation, since there are no special norms of criminal or administrative liability. The criminal law in article 236 of the Criminal Code protects a judge, prosecutor, investigator or person conducting an inquiry from interference in their activities [5]. The exception here is the lawyer.

Only Article 1971 of the Code of Administrative Liability provides for liability for obstructing the professional activities of a lawyer, expressed in failure to provide, untimely submission or submission of knowingly false or unreliable information (documents) to a lawyer's request, as well as influence in any form on a lawyer with the aim of prevent his participation in the case or force him to take a position that is contrary to the interests of the principal (client) [6].

In our time, it is not surprising that a lawyer is called as a witness in the case of a representative of his interests, searches are carried out in a law office, and so on.

Such violations of officials can be qualified under Article 205 of the Criminal Code as abuse of official powers, however, this requires such signs as a significant violation of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens or organizations or legally protected interests of society or the state.

On this, the protective norms of the regime of attorney-client privilege are exhausted. In essence, the law provides for one general criminal law for malpractice, which may still include breach of attorney-client confidentiality. Accordingly, such a weak mechanism for protecting client-client secrets leads to various violations of it, and sometimes to neglect by public authorities and administration officials.

Non-compliance with the regime of attorney-client privilege is becoming something commonplace. Thus, in criminal proceedings, public defense lawyers usually provide a copy of the agreement with the citizen; a copy of an application, complaint, petition (except for court cases), a request, a statement of claim to the court of first instance, appeals, cassation, supervisory complaints; a copy of the judicial act, minutes of the court session. These documents should be submitted for the payment of a lawyer, confirmation of the provision of free legal assistance. This approach clearly contradicts the provisions of Article 9 of the Law "On the Bar", as well as Article 15 of the Rules for the Professional Ethics of Lawyers [7], which explicitly states that attorney-client privilege applies to:

the fact that the principals (clients) applied to the lawyer, including their names and titles;

all evidence and documents collected by the lawyer in the course of preparation for the case;
 information received by the lawyer from the principals (clients);
 information about the principal (client), which became known to the lawyer in the process of providing legal assistance;
 the content of legal advice given directly to the principal (client) or intended for him;
 the entire legal proceeding in the case;
 the terms of the agreement on the provision of legal assistance, including financial settlements between the lawyer and the principal (client);
 any other information related to the provision of legal assistance by a lawyer.

What explains the situation described above? This is because all the documents and information are allegedly needed to control the targeted use of budget funds. The question arises about the priorities of the activities of state authorities, and despite the fact that they have a normatively defined absolute character, the lawyer does not stand for the observance of the privileges of the principal. At the same time, the limits of the rights of a lawyer to provide free legal assistance should in no way be limited [8].

Confidentiality in the provision of free legal assistance means a ban on disclosure to third parties of information that became known to the person providing it in the process of communicating with the principal [9].

Legal regime of attorney-client privilege

Attorney secrecy cannot be absolute. There are special circumstances in which a lawyer may refuse to retain his or her attorney's privileges. For example, defending the position of a lawyer in disciplinary proceedings. The question of whether attorney-client secrecy can be absolute was found in the study of Doctor of Law Yu. S. Pilipenko. He thus concluded that the lawyer's secrecy was relatively absolute. It considered the question of whether counsel was free to determine the circumstances in which counsel could waive his obligations of confidentiality. Such a right of the lawyer-client to waive the obligation to maintain confidentiality is possible in the event of obtaining information about a particularly grave or especially grave crime [10]. In this situation, limiting the limit of attorney-client secrecy is justified, since we are talking about the life and health of the individual, which, in accordance with the norms of international law and the Constitution, is the highest value. Accordingly, the question arises: can the observance of budgetary discipline be the basis for limiting the limit of attorney-client privilege. In order to answer this question, it is necessary to understand why attorney-client privilege is needed when providing legal assistance to socially unprotected citizens. In his research, Yu. S. Pilipenko determines that attorney-client secrecy is a state of prohibition of access to information constituting its content, through the establishment of a special regime.

The legal regime of attorney-client secrecy is a special procedure for legal regulation that operates in the field of qualified legal assistance, aimed at creating and protecting the inviolability of the principal, prohibiting unauthorized access, disclosure of what is known to the lawyer. The legal regime of attorney-client privilege is the most important and necessary condition for the full implementation of these constitutional rights, as well as for obtaining such assistance [10]. The release of a lawyer from the obligation to testify about the circumstances and information that became known to him or was entrusted in connection with his professional activities serves to ensure the right of everyone to privacy, personal and family

secrets, protection of his honor and good name and is a guarantee that information about private life confidentially entrusted by a person for his own protection only to a lawyer will not be used against the will of this person for other purposes.

The provision of free legal assistance affects various areas of private life [11]. Thus, the provision of free legal assistance is possible in disputes about establishing and challenging paternity (maternity), collecting alimony, establishing adoption, guardianship or guardianship of orphans and children left without parental care, limiting legal capacity, appealing against violations of the rights and freedoms of citizens in the provision of psychiatric care, eviction from residential premises, etc. [12]

Citizens who turn to a lawyer and trust information about their family and private life are subject to a number of third-party investigations. Given the level of legal culture and the lack of effective mechanisms for protecting privacy, citizens are less likely to become victims of gossip, not to mention the content of the crime in the form of divulging the secrets of adoption [13].

Thus, the question of priorities arises. On one side of the scale is the right of citizens to privacy, and on the other - budgetary discipline. The need to limit attorney-client privilege in order to comply with the targeted spending of budgetary funds does not find its reasonable justification. We are faced with a situation where the interests of the state dominate the interests of the individual. In the period of the forthcoming reform of the legal profession, when one of its tasks is to increase the status of a lawyer, special attention should be paid to the problem of advocacy secrecy [14].

It is necessary to include protective legal norms in the criminal legislation. In addition, in the absence of a response from law enforcement agencies, the team of lawyers should not allow such a violation of the basic principles of advocacy, since a demonstration of loyalty can lead to a more serious violation of attorney-client privilege.

There are trends towards this: the growth of international terrorism, extremism, drug trafficking, the organization of criminal communities, etc. Under this pretext, a lawyer can turn into the main witness for the prosecution, which will destroy the whole meaning of advocacy.

Limits of attorney-client privilege

An analysis of the scientific literature testifies to the lack of unity in establishing the boundaries and limits of attorney-client privilege. The absence of a unified professional position on this issue creates conditions for abuses that can harm the legally protected interests of citizens.

The identified problem is complex and can be investigated from several angles. The issue of lawyer's confidentiality is directly related to the ethical principles of advocacy, and it must be admitted that today there are no ready-made recipes for resolving ethical disputes that arise in this practice. There are also legislative and practical issues related to the confidentiality of legal aid.

We would like to dwell on this group of problems in more detail.

First, the problem of confidentiality of legal assistance provided by persons who are not lawyers. According to open data, there are about three thousand lawyers. Meanwhile, there are incomparably more people who do not have the status of a lawyer, but who provide legal services on a permanent basis.

The Constitution guarantees everyone the right to receive qualified legal assistance, which in principle cannot exist without trust between the client and the lawyer. Therefore, the secrecy

of the consultation protects, first of all, citizens who need help, and not the lawyer who provides it. The Eighth United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders in 1990 established the Basic Principles on the Role of Lawyers.

These recommendations, in particular, provided guarantees for the performance of their duties by lawyers, in particular ensuring the recognition and confidentiality of any communication and consultations within the professional relationship between lawyers and their clients. However, the legislation does not recognize the right to confidentiality of legal advice for persons who do not have the status of a lawyer. The exclusion of such relations from the list of privileges protected by attorney-client privilege creates a legal basis for discrimination and violation of the right to a profession.

But it seems to us that the violation of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens who use such assistance is more significant, since each appeal to lawyers turns into an act of confession before a witness who does not have the right to refuse to testify against his client. There are only two possible ways out of this problem. The first is the extension of the right to confidentiality of consultation to all persons providing legal assistance, as provided for by the above recommendations, as well as in a number of foreign countries, for example, in England and the USA [15].

The second is the universal “advocacy” of lawyers. However, the latter solution is unrealistic, and it does not answer the question about the secrecy of consultations with corporate lawyers. Secondly, a significant problem is the widespread practice of questioning lawyers as witnesses about the circumstances of the proceedings at the stage of preliminary investigation and the recognition of such evidence as admissible by the courts considering the case [16].

As rightly noted by Yu. Yu. Churilov, the lawyer became “needed by the investigator, first of all, as a witness to consolidate the confession of the suspect (accused) and confirm the legality of the procedural actions carried out with the participation of the lawyer” [17]. We believe that the described practice is contrary to the law, undermines public confidence in the institution of the legal profession, assigns functions to lawyers that are not characteristic of them, and should be stopped.

Thirdly, the problem of maintaining lawyer secrecy during tax audits has already been raised in science [10]. In our opinion, it consists in the fundamental difference between legal assistance and other types of economic activity. This is perhaps the only area of public life regulated by tax legislation where the taxpayer (lawyer) is not required to disclose his counterparty (client). But are there effective financial control mechanisms in this case?

In science, it was proposed to exempt lawyers from paying taxes, and in return to oblige them to provide free assistance for the purpose. But, in our opinion, in this case, we run the risk of involving the legal community in financial fraud and the fall in the authority of the legal profession, which is a greater evil. One of the possible ways out of this situation may be the recognition of malicious tax evasion as an unconditional basis for the termination of the status of a lawyer, as behavior that undermines the trust of society.

Closely related to the previous problem is the problem of the relationship between lawyer secrecy and banking secrecy. Attorney secrecy includes not only information received from the client, but also the fact of his application for legal assistance, as well as the terms of the agreement on the provision of legal assistance, including cash settlements between the lawyer

and the principal. This information may be contained in bank documents and registers. Meanwhile, the current legislation does not contain special restrictions on a bank account agreement with a lawyer. As a result, all ordinary users of banking secrecy have access to lawyer secrecy.

In particular, law enforcement agencies have the right to request bank statements containing both the name of the payer and the purpose of the payment. We believe that in this case, the rights of persons seeking legal assistance are infringed. The way out of this situation would be the introduction of abbreviated forms for the provision of information for the lawyer's bank accounts at the request of state bodies, containing only information about the amount of payment and its generalized purpose.

And finally, in our opinion, a serious problem of legislative regulation of attorney-client privilege is the contradiction between the norms of the Law "On the Bar" and the Law "On Counteracting the Legalization of Proceeds from Crime, the Financing of Terrorism and the Financing of Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction". Article 15 of the Law "On Counteracting the Legalization of Proceeds from Crime, the Financing of Terrorism and the Financing of Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction" obliges a lawyer to send reports of suspicious transactions to a specially authorized state body, including attempts to commit them, in the prescribed manner no later than one business day following the day they were discovered. In particular, such transactions include operations with real estate, activities for the creation of organizations and some others. At the same time, part 2 of article 18 establishes that the provision in the established manner of information on transactions with funds or other property of legal entities and individuals or other information to a specially authorized state body is not a violation of commercial, banking or other secrets protected by law.

But after all, the law understands under lawyer secrecy any information related to the provision of legal assistance by a lawyer to his client. It turns out that the legislator, within the framework of one law, establishes a legal obligation to keep secrets, and cancels it in another.

In science, attempts have been made to resolve this conflict. In particular, V. F. Anisimov and O. S. Rudik expressed the following position: "Turning to the theory of law, in the event of a conflict between a previously valid norm and a later adopted norm contained in acts of the same level, the later adopted norm has priority. This provision is one of the general legal principles for the application of law..." [18].

In our opinion, it is hardly possible to agree with this position. The rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen determine the meaning, content and application of laws, the activities of the legislative and executive authorities and are ensured by justice. Meanwhile, it is rightly noted that "... everyone is guaranteed the right to receive qualified legal assistance ... One of these conditions is to ensure the confidentiality of information, the receipt and use of which is associated with the provision of legal assistance, which by its nature implies trust in relations between a lawyer and a client, what, in particular, is the institution of attorney-client privilege..." [10].

Moreover, if it is recognized that the law allows "denunciation" of a client in cases related to property crimes, then how should the legal profession treat reports of serious crimes against a person that have not been identified, but have become known to them? We believe that the

current wording of the law is controversial and is unlikely to be effective in combating money laundering (regarding the regulation of advocacy).

Conclusions and offers

In conclusion, we consider it necessary to note that the modern state consistently upholds the right of citizens to attorney-client privilege. The revealed problems of the confidentiality of the relationship between the lawyer and the principal, although they are not so acute, however, the implementation of the principle of legality in state activity will largely depend on their speedy solution.

The Law “On Advocacy and Legal Assistance” of 2018 caused heated discussions in society in the Republic of Kazakhstan in terms of ideas regarding the independence of the bar, the introduction of a state bar and other problems.

A number of theoretical and practical issues, problems related to the legal status of a lawyer in civil proceedings, remained unresolved.

In particular, within the meaning of paragraphs 2, 8 of part 3 of article 33 of the Law, a lawyer has the right of a lawyer's request to obtain the information he needs, including if such information contains a legal secret, but only if it is necessary in a criminal case [19].

However, even within the framework of criminal proceedings, as stipulated in paragraph 8 of part 3 of article 33 of the new Law, it is not possible to familiarize a lawyer with information constituting a secret due to the contradiction of this provision with other laws. Thus, within the meaning of part 2 of article 17 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On state registration of rights to real estate and transactions with it”, a lawyer is not included in the circle of persons who have the right to request copies of documents from the registration file, such can only be a judge, prosecutor, investigator, bank managers and liquidation commissions. To other persons, the specified information is provided with the consent of the copyright holder [20].

Similar provisions are also provided in part 9 of article 28 of the Entrepreneurial Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, according to the meaning of which only law enforcement agencies and courts can receive information constituting a secret protected by law [21].

However, if necessary, the court may request information constituting the secret of a third party, and the lawyer and his client have the right to get acquainted with it. However, unlike the Code of Criminal Procedure, the Code of Civil Procedure of the Republic of Kazakhstan does not contain requirements for a party in a civil case, or its representative, to request a non-disclosure receipt of information constituting a secret that became known upon acquaintance with a civil case, as is done in criminal cases. At the same time, the legislation does not provide for liability for the disclosure of information that has become known in this way.

For the disclosure of such a secret by a lawyer, including his principal, who may use the secret for other purposes, it is possible to provide for measures of administrative or disciplinary liability in relation to the lawyer. At the time of providing such information, it is possible to provide for the obligatory writing by a lawyer of an appropriate non-disclosure receipt, as is done in criminal proceedings.

We believe that a lawyer who provides qualified legal assistance to his principals, i.e. not in their own interests, having a higher legal education, in most cases, has a higher degree of legal awareness in relation to the person who is assisted. Therefore, the probability of unfair use of secrets by a lawyer seems to be minimal.

In this regard, it is proposed to provide lawyers with the opportunity to get acquainted with a secret protected by law or a certain part of it, both in the course of criminal, and in the course of civil or other legal proceedings, it is also necessary to introduce amendments regarding the timing of consideration of lawyers' requests in the direction of reduction.

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